

Medical University
Prof. Dr. Paraskev Stoyanov
Varna, Bulgaria

Scripta Scientifica Pharmaceutica

volume 13, 2026, supplement 1

ISSN 2367-6000

The logo consists of the letters 'SSP' in a bold, serif font, with a stylized swoosh underneath the letters.

Scripta Scientifica Pharmaceutica

volume 13, 2026, supplement 1

ISSN 2367-6000 (print)
ISSN 2367-5500 (online)

The logo for Scripta Scientifica Pharmaceutica (SSP) features the letters "SSP" in a bold, serif font. A curved line sweeps under the letters from the left, ending under the "P".

Scripta Scientifica Pharmaceutica

An official publication of Medical University "Prof. Dr. Paraskev Stoyanov" of Varna

Editor-in-Chief:

Svetlana Georgieva

Dean, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Varna

Co-Editor-in-Chief:

Veselina Panayotova

Medical University of Varna

Editorial Board:

Adriana Trapani

Aldo Moro University of Bari, Italy

Albena Merdzhanova

Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria

Alexander Zlatkov

Medical University of Sofia, Bulgaria

Anna Todorova

Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria

Bisera Pilicheva

Medical University of Plovdiv, Bulgaria

Carlo Franchini

Aldo Moro University of Bari, Bulgaria

Carlos L. Cespedes Acuna

University of Bio Bio of Casilla Chillan, Chile

Dobri Ivanov

Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria

Evgeni Grigorov

Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria

Galina Aleksieva Yaneva

Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria

Hristina Lebanova

Medical University of Pleven, Bulgaria

Ilko Getov

Medical University of Sofia, Bulgaria

Kalin Ivanov

Medical University of Plovdiv, Bulgaria

Kaloyan Georgiev

Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria

Katarzyna Komosinska-Vassev

Medical University of Silesia in Katowice, Poland

Kristina Mladenovska

Ss. Cyril and Methodius University of Skopje,
North Macedonia

Maya Radeva-Ilieva

Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria

Milen Georgiev

Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Bulgaria

Milka Nashar

Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria

Nadya Agova

Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria

Ola Ghaleb Ahmed Al Ahdab Albannay

College of Pharmacy University of Sharjah,
United Arab Emirates

Pawel Olczyk

Medical University of Silesia in Katowice, Poland

Philip J. Wiffen

Churchill Hospital of Oxford, United Kingdom

Robert Gaspar

University of Szeged, Hungary

Roberto Frontini
University Hospital of Leipzig, Germany

Süreyya Ölgen
University of Ankara, Turkey

Ticuta Negreanu-Pirjol
Ovidius University of Constanta, Romania

Velichka Andonova
Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria

Victoriya Georgiyants
National University of Pharmacy - Kharkov, Ukraine

Section Editors:

Ivelin Iliev
Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria

Veselina Panayotova
Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria

Design and Layout Editing:

Emilia Yordanova
Publishing Department,
Medical University of Varna

Web Design and Development:

Ognyan Antov
Publishing Department,
Medical University of Varna

Proofreading:

Yordanka Peteva
Publishing Department,
Medical University of Varna

FIRST SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

VARNA PHARMACOLOGICAL DAYS

Jubilee Scientific Forum Dedicated to:

The 65th Anniversary of the Establishment of the Medical University of Varna

The 65th Anniversary of the Foundation of the Department of Pharmacology

*The 10th Anniversary of the Establishment of the Department of Pharmacology,
Toxicology and Pharmacotherapy at the Faculty of Pharmacy*

*The 100th Anniversary of the Birth of Prof. Delcho Zhelyazkov, MD—Founder of
the Medical University of Varna and Creator of the Department of Pharmacology*

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Varna, Bulgaria

May 29–31, 2026

Scientific Committee:

Stefka Vasileva Valcheva-Kuzmanova, Medical University of Varna

Maria Delcheva Zhelyazkova-Savova, Medical University of Varna

Kaloyan Dobrinov Georgiev, Medical University of Varna

Marieta Petrova Georgieva, Medical University of Varna

Maya Petrova Radeva-Ilieva, Medical University of Varna

Silvia Gancheva Marinova, Medical University of Varna

Nadezhda Rumenova Kirkkeselyan, Medical University of Varna

Miroslav Tsonkov Eftimov, Medical University of Varna

Stela Toshkova Dragomanova, Medical University of Varna

Antoaneta Borisova Georgieva, Medical University of Varna

Stanila Seryozheva Stoeva-Grigorova, Medical University of Varna

Organizing Committee:

Kaloyan Dobrinov Georgiev, Medical University of Varna

Maya Petrova Radeva-Ilieva, Medical University of Varna

Silvia Gancheva Marinova, Medical University of Varna

Nadezhda Rumenova Kirkkeselyan, Medical University of Varna

Stela Toshkova Dragomanova, Medical University of Varna

Antoaneta Borisova Georgieva, Medical University of Varna

Stanila Seryozheva Stoeva-Grigorova, Medical University of Varna

Elitsa Aleksandrova Stoychev, Medical University of Varna

Zornitsa Ivanova Nikolova, Medical University of Varna

CONTENTS

Stefka Vasileva Valcheva-Kuzmanova - POLYPHENOLS IN THE FOCUS OF PHARMACOLOGICAL RESEARCH. WHAT IS OUR EXPERIENCE? _____	13
Kaloyan D. Georgiev - MODERN PHARMACOLOGY: HISTORY, CHALLENGES, AND PROSPECTS _____	14
Delyan Delev - ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND PHARMACOLOGY: TRANSFORMING DRUG DEVELOPMENT AND PATIENT CARE _____	15
Lyudmil Peychev - HOMEOPATHY AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE—CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES _____	16
Jana Tchekalarova, Petya Ivanova, Violina T. Angelova - THE ROLE OF THE MELATONIN SYSTEM IN ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE: PATHOGENIC MECHANISMS AND THERAPEUTIC PROSPECTS _____	17
Emil Hristov - UNDERSTANDING THE PHARMACOKINETIC VARIABILITY OF BIOLOGICALS, BIOSIMILARS, AND BIOBETTERS—A VIEW POINT TOWARDS MONOCLONAL ANTIBODIES _____	18
Diana Pendicheva-Duhlenka - PHARMACOGENOMICS AT A CLINICAL CROSSROADS: A REVOLUTION IN WAITING _____	19
Pavlina Gateva - CLINICALLY SIGNIFICANT PHARMACOKINETIC FEATURES IN OBESITY AND DIABETES _____	20
Emil Gatchev - ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE: THE ROLE OF THE CLINICAL PHARMACOLOGIST _____	21
Galya Stavreva - FROM THE LAB TO THE CANVAS: THE REMEDY IN FINE ART _____	22
Rumen Nikolov - FACTOR XI/XIa INHIBITORS: PROGRESS IN ANTICOAGULANT THERAPY _____	23
Melis Ahmedova, Miroslav Eftimov, Maria Zhelyazkova-Savova, Svetlana Georgieva, Miglena Nikolova, Oskan Tasinov, Silvia Gancheva - AMELIORATION OF SCOPOLAMINE-INDUCED COGNITIVE IMPAIRMENT BY <i>KOCHIA SCOPARIA</i> EXTRACT IN RATS: EVIDENCE FROM THE ACTIVE AVOIDANCE PARADIGM _____	24
Nadezhda Ivanova, Velichka Andonova - HYDROCOLLOID MATRICES AS SUSTAINED DRUG DELIVERY PLATFORMS FOR DILTIAZEM _____	25
Iliyan Bogdanov, Milen Hristov, Pavlina Gateva - THE ROLE OF TIRZEPATIDE IN DIABETIC NEUROPATHY IN MICE MODEL _____	26
Kristina Stavrakeva, Elisaveta Apostolova, Vesela Kokova, Mariyan Topolov, Ivica Dimov, Mariya Choneva, Delyan Delev, Ilija Kostadinov, Iliya Bivolarski, Maria Koleva, Rumen Mladenov, Plamen Stoyanov, Anelia Bivolarska - EFFECTS OF METHANOLIC EXTRACT OF <i>MICROMERIA FRIVALDSZKYANA</i> ON LOCOMOTOR ACTIVITY AND ACTIVE LEARNING IN RATS _____	27
Elis Rafailova, Maria Tzaneva, Nadezhda Stefanova, Milena Todorova, Silvia Gancheva, Miroslav Eftimov, Klementina Moneva-Marinova, Mehmed Reysov, Maria Zhelyazkova-Savova, Stefka Valcheva-Kuzmanova - EFFECTS OF PRETREATMENT WITH ANETHOLE IN A MODEL OF PARACETAMOL-INDUCED HEPATOTOXICITY IN RATS _____	29
Maria Petrova, Desislava Ilieva-Tonova, Stanila Stoeva-Grigorova, Maya Radeva-Ilieva - EMERGING PHARMACOTHERAPEUTIC STRATEGIES IN SCHIZOPHRENIA: A NARRATIVE REVIEW AND REGULATORY CLINICAL TRIAL REGISTRY ANALYSIS _____	30
Elif Mehmedova, Viliana Gugleva - BETULINIC ACID: PHARMACOLOGICAL EFFECTS, MECHANISMS OF ACTION, AND THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL _____	31
Gabriela Panayotova, Antoniya Hachmeriyan - LIMITING FACTORS AND ETHICAL CHALLENGES IN THE APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PHARMACOLOGY _____	32

Tsvetelina Stefanova, Evgeni Grigorov, Galina Petrova, Ivo Filipov - STRATEGIES FOR DEVELOPING CLINICAL PHARMACY SERVICES IN AMBULATORY CARE: A HEMATOLOGY PERSPECTIVE _____	33
Petya Tsoneva, Nadezhda Hvarchanova, Stanila Stoeva-Grigorova, Maya Radeva-Ilieva - SAFETY OF RED YEAST RICE SUPPLEMENTS: CONTAMINANTS AND VARIABILITY _____	34
Antoniya Andonova, Elif Mehmedova, Nadezhda Hvarchanova, Viliana Gugleva - MODERN NANOTECHNOLOGICAL APPROACHES FOR OPTIMIZING THE SAFETY OF BENZOYL PEROXIDE IN ACNE TREATMENT _____	35
Ivo Filipov, Velina Chervenkova, Tsvetelina Stefanova, Evgeni Grigorov - CLINICAL IMPACT OF DRUG-DRUG INTERACTIONS ON PATIENT SAFETY AND OUTCOMES IN CLINICAL TRIALS: THE ROLE OF THE HOSPITAL PHARMACIST _____	36
Zornitsa Nikolova, Stefka Valcheva-Kuzmanova - EXPERIMENTAL ANIMAL MODELS FOR THE EVALUATION OF ANTI-ULCER ACTIVITY IN THE STOMACH _____	37
Kaloyan Ivanov, Silvia Gancheva - NEUROPHARMACOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF <i>ZIZIPHUS JUJUBA</i> EXTRACTS: A REVIEW OF EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES _____	38
Raya Velcheva, Velichka Andonova - ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES AGAINST GRAM-POSITIVE, GRAM-NEGATIVE BACTERIA, AND FUNGI _____	39
Liliya Pashova-Stoyanova, Darko Simonov, Dimitar Berbatov, Maya Gulubova, Anna Tolekova - OBESITY AND METABOLIC DYSFUNCTION IN PATIENTS WITH OBSTRUCTIVE SLEEP APNEA _____	40
Simeon Georgiev, Nasie Asipova, Adelin Kadiev, Antoan Rangelov - MEDICAL DEVICES CONTAINING MEDICINAL SUBSTANCES: THEIR ROLE IN PHARMACOTHERAPY AND REGULATORY CHALLENGES _____	41
Nikolay Nachev, Yoana Nikolaeva, Antoan Rangelov, Stefka Stoyanova, Emanuil Yordanov, Emil Hristov - APPROACHES FOR ASSESSING THE PHOTOTOXICITY OF COSMETIC PRODUCTS AND COSMETIC INGREDIENTS—A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW _____	42
Mila Bukarova, Anna Todorova, Natalya Usheva - METFORMIN AND LIFESTYLE MODIFICATIONS: A SYNERGISTIC APPROACH TO POTENTIATE THE METABOLIC RESPONSE _____	44
Stamen Bankovski, Magdalena Pesheva, Evgeni Grigorov - QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE PENETRATION OF ADVANCED THERAPY MEDICINAL PRODUCTS IN EUROPE _____	45
Gloria Dimitrova, Silviya Mihaylova, Silvia Gancheva - EXPERIMENTAL MODELS OF PSORIASIS: COMPARATIVE EVALUATION AND TRANSLATIONAL PERSPECTIVES _____	46
Tsvetomir Aleksandrov, Miroslav Eftimov, Evgeni Grigorov - HOSPITAL PHARMACIST-LED MONITORING FOR PATIENTS TREATED WITH CAPECITABINE OR ABEMACICLIB: A PROSPECTIVE APPROACH FOR OPTIMIZATION OF ORAL ANTICANCER THERAPY _____	47
Danail Pavlov, Miroslav Eftimov, Antoaneta Georgieva, Mehmed Reyzov, Milena Todorova, Nadezhda Stefanova, Maria Tzaneva, Miglena Nikolova, Zlatina Gospodinova, Georgi Antov, Miroslav Novakovic, Vele Tesevic, Natalia Krasteva, Stefka Valcheva-Kuzmanova - PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF FUSTIN ISOLATED FROM <i>COTINUS COGGYRIA</i> HEARTWOOD _____	48
Dayana Manuelyan, Daniela Pechlivanova - SEX-DEPENDENT DIFFERENCES IN BEHAVIOR RESPONSES TO LPS-INDUCED IMMUNE STRESS IN JUVENILE RATS _____	50
Natalia Vilmosh, Maria Georgieva-Kotetarova, Ilin Kandilarov, Hristina Zlatanova-Tenisheva, Iliya Kostadinov, Delyan Delev, Maria Dimitrova - COMPARATIVE EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF THE ANTI-INFLAMMATORY AND ANALGESIC ACTIVITY OF A CO ₂ EXTRACT OF <i>SATUREJA MONTANA</i> AND CARVACROL _____	51
Darinka Dimitrova, Kremena Saracheva, Yordanka Uzunova, Nikolay Toshev - NANOPARTICLES AS DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS _____	52

Liliya Pashova-Stoyanova, Zhivka Tsokeva, Tsvetelin Georgiev, Petya Hadzhibozheva, Maria Ganeva, Anna Tolekova - EFFECTS OF DIFFERENT DOSES OF VITAMIN D ON MORPHOMETRIC PARAMETERS OF ANIMALS WITH METABOLIC DISORDERS	53
Galya Stavreva, Plamena Panayotova, Boris Dinkov, Violina Ivanova, Teodora Alexandrova, Alexandar Pashev, Regina Komsa-Penkova - METFORMIN AND COLLAGEN GLYCATION IN EXPERIMENTAL TYPE 2 DIABETES: ATR-FTIR ANALYSIS	54
Plamena Panayotova, Boris Dinkov, Venka Tsankova, Maya Gulubova - EFFECTS OF METFORMIN ON PANCREATIC MORPHOLOGY IN A CHRONIC HIGH-FAT DIET/STREPTOZOTOCIN TYPE 2 DIABETES	55
Milen Hristov, Vesela Ivanova, Tihomir Dikov, Pavlina Gateva - TARGETING DIABETIC SKIN: LIRAGLUTIDE REVERSES EPIDERMAL THINNING AND INCREASES TRPV1 EXPRESSION	56
Daniela Pechlivanova, Borislav Assenov, Petya Ivanova, Galina Stoyancheva, Petar Todorov - EFFECTS OF AN ANGIOTENSIN 1-7 ANALOG ON CHRONIC ANGIOTENSIN-CONVERTING ENZYME TYPE 2 INHIBITION-INDUCED ALTERATIONS IN GENE EXPRESSION, INFLAMMATION, AND MEMORY	57
Olya Videnova, Stefka Stoyanova, Antoan Rangelov, Emanuil Yordanov, Eliza Hristova - REPORTING LEVEL OF ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS—A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS BETWEEN BULGARIA AND EU MEMBER STATES	58
Viktoria Ilieva, Irfan Irfan, Yordanka Yamakova, Dobrin Svinarov - TREATMENT OF MULTI-RESISTANT <i>KLEBSIELLA PNEUMONIAE</i> WITH GENTAMYCIN BASED ON PHARMACOKINETIC MODELING IN A CRITICALLY ILL PATIENT WITH ACUTE KIDNEY INJURY: A CASE REPORT	60
Ivan Lalovski, Margarita Krasteva, Emanuil Yordanov, Emil Hristov, Iva Parvova - METHYLEUGENOL—FOOD OR POISON?	61
Antoniya Hachmeriyan, Minka Hristova - PEPTIDE-BASED APPROACHES IN WOUND HEALING: EMERGING REGENERATIVE STRATEGIES	62
Sirma Angelova, Milena Georgieva - MEDICINE AND FOOD SUPPLEMENT INTAKE AS A CO-FACTOR FOR THE ORAL HEALTH STATUS IN CHILDREN WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER	63
Boris Dinkov, Genka Krasteva, Nikolinka Koleva, Evgenia Tsoleva, Diana Pendicheva-Duhhlenska - THE GUT MICROBIOME AS A POTENTIAL MODULATOR OF GLP-1-BASED THERAPIES IN MASLD/MASH	64
Emanuil Yordanov, Stefka Stoyanova, Simeon Georgiev, Lyubina Todorova ¹ Daniela Seymenska, Iva Parvova - APPROACHES FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF THE MICROBIOLOGICAL QUALITY OF COSMETIC PRODUCTS—A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW	65
Nicolinka Koleva, Boris Dinkov, Evgenia Tsoleva, Galya Stavreva - THE ROLE OF SNAC AS AN ABSORPTION ENHANCER: MECHANISM OF ACTION AND CLINICAL RELEVANCE	67
Genka Krasteva, Venka Tsankova, Nikolinka Stoyanova, Boris Dinkov, Ioana Nikolova - GUT MICROBIOTA—DRUG INTERACTIONS IN CARDIOVASCULAR PHARMACOLOGY: IMPLICATIONS FOR PERSONALIZED THERAPY	68
Yoana Sotirova, Katya Sotirova - ADVANCES IN THE THERAPEUTIC USE OF NEUROKININ-1 RECEPTOR ANTAGONISTS: EXPANDING BEYOND ANTIEMETIC INDICATIONS	69
Yoana Sotirova, Katya Sotirova - NANOTECHNOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO ENHANCE THE BIOAVAILABILITY OF NEUROKININ-1 RECEPTOR ANTAGONISTS: A FOCUS ON APREPITANT	70
Todor Todorov, Tsvetelina Stefanova - REGULATORY CHALLENGES IN EXPANDING CLINICAL PHARMACY PRACTICE IN HOSPITAL SETTINGS	71

Georgi Maksimov, Lubina Todorova, Bogdan Kirilov - PATHOGENETIC PHARMACOTHERAPY WITH VORASIDENIB IN IDH1 C.395G>A P.R132H-MUTATED GRADE II ASTROCYTOMA _____	72
Neli Krumova, Stanila Stoeva-Grigorova, Ivanesa Yarabanova, Ivelina Panayotova, Maya Radeva-Ilieva, Georgi Bonchev, Milan Tsekov, Simeon Marinov, Petko Marinov, Snezha Zlateva - POLYSUBSTANCE USE IN THE ERA OF THE FOURTH WAVE OF THE OPIOID CRISIS: A FATAL CASE OF RHABDOMYOLYSIS, ACUTE KIDNEY INJURY, AND DEEP VEIN THROMBOSIS _____	73
Svetlin Slavov, Maya Radeva-Ilieva, Nadezhda Hvarchanova, Stanila Stoeva-Grigorova, Viliana Gugleva, Iliyan Kolev, Velichka Andonova - EVALUATION OF THE ULCEROGENIC AND GASTROPROTECTIVE EFFECTS OF HYPERFORIN IN AN INDOMETHACIN-INDUCED GASTRIC ULCER MODEL IN RATS _____	74
Daniela Gromova, Stanila Stoeva-Grigorova, Stela Dragomanova, Ivanesa Yarabanova, Nadezhda Hvarchanova, Gabriela Kehayova, Maya Radeva-Ilieva, Elitsa Stoychev, Simeonka Dimitrova, Borislav Sevriev, Snezha Zlateva, Petko Marinov - INTRAVENOUS LIPID EMULSION AS AN ADJUVANT STRATEGY IN FENTANYL TOXICITY: EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION ALONE AND IN COMBINATION WITH NALOXONE IN WISTAR RATS _____	75
Ivaylo Georgiev, Ivelin Iliev, Svetlana Georgieva, Melis Ahmedova, Miroslav Eftimov, Miglena Nikolova, Oskan Tasinov, Silvia Gancheva - MOMORDIN IC IN <i>KOCHIA SCOPARIA</i> SEEDS: QUANTIFICATION AND EXTRACTION OPTIMIZATION _____	76
Teya Boneva, Maya Radeva-Ilieva, Stanila Stoeva-Grigorova, Ivanesa Yarabanova, Ivelina Panayotova, Georgi Bonchev, Nadezhda Hvarchanova, Mario Milkov, Simeon Marinov, Petko Marinov, Snezha Zlateva - FATAL ACUTE INTOXICATION WITH HIGH-DOSE CAFFEINE TABLETS: A FULMINANT CASE WITH EXTREME PLASMA LEVELS AND REFRACTORY CARDIOVASCULAR COLLAPSE _____	77
Teya Boneva, Tanya Kazakova, Anna Todorova - NIPOCALIMAB AS A TARGETED THERAPY FOR AUTOIMMUNE DISEASES: A NEW ERA OF FCRN INHIBITION _____	79
Petar Plamenov, Silvia Gancheva - DRUG-DRUG INTERACTION POTENTIAL OF ZOREVUNERSEN WITHIN THE POLYTHERAPEUTIC FRAMEWORK OF DRAVET SYNDROME _____	80
Hadzher Mehmedali, Miroslav Eftimov - COMPARATIVE EFFICACY AND SAFETY OF ANTI-TNF- α AGENTS AND VEDOLIZUMAB IN THE TREATMENT OF CROHN'S DISEASE _____	81
Berna Velieva, Mehmed Reyzov - NOVEL APPROACHES IN THE PHARMACOLOGICAL MANAGEMENT OF PROLIFERATIVE DIABETIC RETINOPATHY _____	82
Georgi Gramatikov, Hristiana Hristova, Miroslav Eftimov - FROM VENOM TO THERAPEUTICS: DEVELOPMENT OF TOXIN-DERIVED DRUGS _____	83
Desislava Karatopraklieva, Silvia Gancheva - BERBERINE AND PREDIABETES: A REVIEW OF ITS POTENTIAL TO DELAY PROGRESSION TO TYPE 2 DIABETES _____	84
Viktor Ivanov, Monika Kartelova, Mehmed Reyzov - REWIRING THE ADDICTED BRAIN: THE EMERGING ROLE OF INCRETIN-RECEPTOR AGONISTS IN SUBSTANCE USE DISORDERS _____	85
Lilyana Ivanova, Momchil Lambev, Plamen Bekyarov, Ivo Rakitin, Dimana Dimitrova, Antoaneta Tsvetkova, Silviya Mihaylova - AI-ASSISTED ADMET PROFILING OF NATURAL PRODUCTS: TOWARD FASTER DRUG DISCOVERY—A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW _____	86
Anton Iliev, Pavlina Koseva, Ivalina Vasileva - PHARMACOLOGICAL POTENTIAL OF COMMON CONSTITUENTS OF PINE ESSENTIAL OIL: A REVIEW _____	87
Stefan Elkov, Michaela Shishmanova-Doseva, Borislava Lechkova, Kremena Saracheva - <i>VERBENA OFFICINALIS</i> IN DERMATOLOGY: A PROMISING NATURAL ANTIMICROBIAL AGENT _____	88

Bilyana Todorova, Borislava Lechkova, Kremena Saracheva, Michaela Shishmanova-Doseva - NEUROPROTECTIVE POTENTIAL OF <i>VERBENA OFFICINALIS</i> L.: EVIDENCE FROM IN VITRO AND IN VIVO STUDIES _____	89
Atanas Krastev, Antoaneta Georgieva - PSYCHEDELIC-ASSISTED THERAPIES IN TREATMENT-RESISTANT PSYCHIATRIC DISORDERS _____	90
Gabriela Angelova, Michaela Shishmanova-Doseva, Darina Barbutska - CARDIOPROTECTIVE POTENTIAL OF GLP-1 RECEPTOR AGONISTS: A REVIEW _____	91
Siyana Ivanova, Daniela Gromova, Marieta Georgieva - NEW PSYCHOACTIVE SUBSTANCES _____	92
Maria Desislava Panayotova, Nadya Agova, Kaloyan Mihalev, Gergana Gecheva, Svetlana Georgieva - PHARMACOLOGICAL POTENTIAL OF CONOTOXINS: FROM MARINE VENOM TO A NEW GENERATION OF ANALGESICS _____	93
Maria Desislava Panayotova, Zvezdelina Velkova, Stela Dragomanova - MIRABEGRON VERSUS VIBEGRON IN THE PHARMACOLOGICAL MANAGEMENT OF OVERACTIVE BLADDER: A NARRATIVE REVIEW OF EFFICACY, SAFETY, AND RISK _____	94
Yoana Hristova, Nikolay Shapkov, Milena Todorova - THE EVOLUTION OF PHARMACOTHERAPY FOR ALCOHOL USE DISORDER: FROM AVERSIVE DETERRENCE TO PRECISION NEURO-MODULATION _____	95
Bayram Shukriev, Momchil Lambev, Plamen Bekyarov, Stanislava Georgieva, Mariya Koleva, Petya Georgieva, Nadya Agova - GLP-1 RECEPTOR AGONISTS AND BONE HEALTH: IMPLICATIONS FOR OSTEOPOROSIS RISK _____	96
Maya Ivanova, Desislava Aleksandrova-Ivanova, Violeta Stoyanova - ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS ASSOCIATED WITH OVER-THE-COUNTER MEDICINES IN THE PEDIATRIC POPULATION _____	97
Kaloyan Dimitrov, Silvia Gancheva - TARGETING THE SIGMA-1 RECEPTOR IN THE TREATMENT OF GLAUCOMA: A REVIEW OF PRECLINICAL EVIDENCE _____	98
Deriya Sebaydin, Silvia Gancheva - PSILOCYBIN-ASSISTED PSYCHOTHERAPY IN TREATMENT-RESISTANT DEPRESSION: A REVIEW OF CURRENT EVIDENCE _____	99
Bilyana Kostadinova, Stanila Stoeva-Grigorova, Nadezhda Hvarchanova, Maya Radeva-Ilieva - NOVEL THERAPEUTIC STRATEGIES FOR OBESITY MANAGEMENT _____	100
Daniela Dimitrova, Gabriela Kehayova, Simeonka Dimitrova, Stela Dragomanova - MARINE NATURAL PRODUCTS AS MULTIFUNCTIONAL MODULATORS IN ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE THERAPY _____	101
GUIDELINES FOR AUTHORS _____	103

STRATEGIES FOR DEVELOPING CLINICAL PHARMACY SERVICES IN AMBULATORY CARE: A HEMATOLOGY PERSPECTIVE

Tsvetelina Stefanova^{1,2}, Evgeni Grigorov², Galina Petrova², Ivo Filipov³

¹*St. Marina University Hospital, Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria*

²*Department of Organization and Economics of Pharmacy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria*

³*St. Georgi University Hospital, Medical University of Plovdiv, Bulgaria*

ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: Patients with hematological malignancies and benign disorders are frequently exposed to high-risk pharmacotherapy requiring close monitoring for toxicity, drug-drug interactions, and medication adherence. Clinical pharmacists are integral members of multidisciplinary teams; however, the organization and impact of ambulatory clinical pharmacy services remain heterogeneous.

AIM: The aim of the study is to systematically evaluate the implementation models and clinical impact of ambulatory clinical pharmacy services in hematology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: A systematic literature review and comparative analysis were conducted across Web of Science, Scopus, Google Scholar, and ResearchGate, focusing on studies addressing ambulatory hematology pharmacy practice.

RESULTS: Evidence supports structured, multifaceted service models based on comprehensive medication management, medication utilization review, and patient-centered care. Pharmacist-led interventions—including medication reconciliation, regimen validation, toxicity monitoring, and management of drug-related problems—improve medication safety and optimize therapy, while adherence support and patient education address key challenges in ambulatory care.

However, substantial heterogeneity in service design, scope, and outcome reporting limits comparability and generalizability. The long-term clinical impact, including survival outcomes, remains insufficiently defined. Inconsistent implementation of standardized documentation and classification frameworks further constrains evaluation. Although multidisciplinary integration is critical for successful implementation, barriers such as limited resources, institutional variability, and inadequate reimbursement persist.

CONCLUSION: Clinical pharmacists constitute a critical component of ambulatory hematology care, enhancing medication safety and therapeutic outcomes. The establishment of standardized service frameworks, harmonized documentation practices, and robust outcome metrics is imperative to substantiate their clinical and economic value.

Keywords: *clinical pharmacy services, ambulatory care, clinical pharmacy, hematology*